

Study of Perception of College Going Young Adults towards Online Streaming Services

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ABSTRACT

The research conducted focuses upon the perception of college going young adults towards online video streaming services. Researcher has worked upon responses gathered from young adults, their perceptions and various options available to them. Researchers collected responses from 120 college going young adults from Pune. The respondents were from the age category of 15 to 25 years of age. The data was collected using google forms and it was analysed using Google's analytical tools. It was found that most of the student services and these services proved to be one of the biggest sources of entertainment for these students. Traditional media is losing its lustre because of various advantages of streaming services. Students admitted that their schedule is affected because of time spent on video streaming services. Today the top three video streaming platforms are YouTube, Netflix and Hotstar.

Keywords-- Video Streaming Services, Traditional Media, Consumer Behaviour, Young Adults

I. INTRODUCTION

It is the time now when media consumption across the world is shifting towards digital model than tradition media. Telecommunication can be considered as the part of human beings as it is deep rooted and it is more of a relationship. Whereas both digital and traditional media in many ways serve as a one-way relationship in which digital media gives viewer the edge over other, because it is you who decides what you want to watch, when you want to watch, where you want to watch.

This shift is the result of increased connectivity, increased speed of internet, increased data size and many other such elements which is result of competition between telecomm companies, which in result give access to the internet to more people day by day, and after they have the access they will definitely try to use it, So out of everything being watched across the world, there is one online streaming service which is on the top of list in terms of data consumed overall and that is Netflix, consuming 15 % of global net traffic, according to research from bandwidth management company Sandvine (Cullen, 2018).

Out of this population, if we split it according to age demographics, according to a website there were more than 74 % of people under the age of 35 years who

were using the internet, which gives us a clear insight that most of them are teenagers and college going students. For college going young adults, online streaming services suit almost the best. Amidst their classroom schedule, workshops, projects, whenever one feels like watching something, they can freely watch using online streaming services. These online streaming services offer their streams through different medium i.e. through website, which means it can be accessed through smart televisions, desktops, laptops and also there are mobile application for it, which means that it can be accessed via mobile phones, tablets etc. which is far more comfortable and easy for one to access rather than sitting in front of television.

II. OBJECTIVES

- To study the consumption behaviour of video streaming services
- To study influence of online video streaming services on college going young adults.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is exploratory in nature. The researcher used structured questionnaire to collect the data analyzing variables like perception towards streaming services, category wise influence on people's approach and peer influence, studying daily regimes. Likert scale technique was used in the questionnaire to get responses and to collect either a favorable or unfavorable attitude towards asked questions.

IV. SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The researchers used convenience sampling for the data collection.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research paper by Hemant Joshi (Joshi, 2015) as the topic already suggests that the main focus of this paper is upon the digital content and online streaming services as the author is talking from a company's point of view so a little bit of smart advertising can be seen in the starting lines of paragraph as the aim of company is

being projected through the medium of this paper. Coming to the main topic, author tries to cover different monetization models and how Indian companies are trying to find out the best possible model for digital content in India also how the author has used the statistics in a very good manner and used them in explaining the model applicable in India also in this author says that revolution in telecomm sector had a huge impact on streaming services as the process of data were at one time low and people were more inclined towards online streaming because of free data and other factors such as increase in internet speed and also tells how streaming companies are using hybrid models to attract customers and also they are doing this to test out the best models which could be used to its maximum. Also it focuses on music streaming and the quality of streaming. In a case study, the author (ROGINSKA, 2014) observed that due to large scale reach of internet and cloud computing, every day the opportunities are increasing also the way they conveyed the presence of internet everywhere by the help of word omnipresent and also it is the study conducted on Europe so the present situation of all the internet related facilities is discussed and also the emphasis is more based upon the efficiency also we can see how the Europe is being compared to whole world and in this paper it is sad that Europe is behind many countries in terms of mobile data and connectivity and for that many recommendations like free movement of goods online, clear mobile data connectivity, also to introduce a single market act.

Benjamin In this research (Burroughs, 2015) says that basically streaming can be seen from two different perspectives and also tells that due to online streaming services the traditional cable operating system are standing face to face and which can be a matter of tension between these platforms and can cause some problems on small grounds but the harsh reality is that online streaming is the future of televisions.

Aoife Coffey through (Coffey, 2016) her paper tries to explain us all that companies she choose are Apple, Spotify and tidal also tell about their history and workings also the author talks about piracy in the music industry and also it is discussed that the reach of the music streaming services is very vast and its numbers are in millions and shows the transition took place from cassettes, ds to mobile phones and also these companies keep an eye on websites which makes latest songs free downloadable to people because there might be malware risks in them the increase in internet availability helped music streaming sites to grow at such rates also tactic like free trails and low subscription rates attract people towards this sites

In this research (Sharma, 2016) paper, the Netflix is at the limelight of the show and also it is told that how is causing the disruption between the traditional

media and it is the basic compassion between the working models of both the media as it is told that how complication is the traditional cable operating system as compared to online streaming services.

Darrell tells us that (West, 2014) what possible future of online media streaming services can look like it takes into consideration the roles of people, business and governance and how the new models are being designed to be more flexible, adaptive, and cost effective but it also worries about the sectors of the societies where these services would be very hard to cater. Or the jest of research can be this that the author related the human behaviour of visually pairing everything it learns quickly by visually seeing it so these streaming sites also use this characteristic of human being to attract them.

About 6 in 10 young adults in USA primarily use online streaming (Centre, 2017) to watch television. The survey marks the latest in a number of Pew Research Centre findings that show to what extent the internet and apps have shifted people's access pathways to media and some types of content in last few years. For example, the internet has now become television as a source of news in the U.S. A generation ago, television was certainly the dominant news source for Americans, but now, the internet substantially overtakes TV as a regular news source for adults younger than 50.

The high cost of cable and the comparatively lower cost of unlimited internet were widely highlighted by respondents (Bozkurt, 2016). Second to cost was the issue of choice. As per the consumer demand, people may make such decisions due to stick to some specific content on cable services or online streaming. Respondents also cited reasons like Convenience—including the ability to pause and rewind live TV, being able to record a TV show or being able to watch online whenever you want and pick up exactly where you left off.

Netflix and Video Streaming (Raba, 2014) the remediation of the video rental store into the consumer's home. Video Streaming is a technology that has completely transformed the entertainment industry as well as consumption models among the audience members. A lot has changed since that very first Real Player transmission in 1995. Since then, technology has been constantly improving, making content delivery and access easier no matter the platform trying to access it.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION

1. Nearly 95.6 students confirmed that they use online vid streaming services. In digital age, this shows how youth is inclined towards consuming the global content on international service providers like Netflix, amazon, hotstar.

Streaming services usage preference of respondents

(Source: Authors' own contribution)

2. There is growing competition among these tech giants as to growing demand of these services with YouTube attracting 92.6% viewership. 64% responded that they watch Netflix, 53.7 watching amazon prime. Hot star, Sony which are known for showing more Indian content are popular among 55.9 and 30 % students. Other services watched by students include Voot, Jio, and Torrents etc.

3. Online streaming services are one of the major sources of entertainment they are increasingly becoming part of

daily lives of student. Over 59% students claimed they use these services every day. Nearly 30 % said they use these services once n couple of day's depending on their college schedules.

4. Almost 83% of the people choose online streaming services over traditional media because they want to watch their choice of show at their own time, unlike television shows which are aired on particular days and time

Reasons for the choice of a particular video streaming service

(Source: Authors' own contribution)

5. It was noted that 36.3% people watch these services for 30-60 minutes every day and almost 29 % watching it over 1 hour.

6. It was observed from the responses that 86% people watch services because they want entertainment and also 55 % people believed that they have their personnel interest in services.

7. 74% people which use online video streaming services voted for thriller genre, and almost 67 % people opted for comedy shows or series and 57 % people prefer fiction genre over others genres, which tells us that this huge list of genre also contribute to the reason that why people watch online streaming service more.

8. It was recorded from responses of survey that 34% agree that there daily schedule is affected by the services and 27 % people said that usually their schedule is affected and 12 % don't agree that their schedule is not affected by online streaming services.

9. When asked about subscription of these services 40 % people believed that some services are costly and 19 % believed that fee of these services are worth the amount.

10. Over 71% prefer one streaming service over its competitors because of exclusive shows broadcasted by it. Nearly 36% claimed features as one of the preferred factors. Other prominent factors included layout, streaming quality, peer influence.

11. After watching completion of a series or content, nearly 21% students relate it to their own lives. 53 % claimed to relate to the content sometimes and 18 % denied relating any content to their real lives.

12. Nearly 57 % students believed that watching these shows changed their way of thinking or perception towards reality. 26% believed no changes were seen in

their way off thinking. 11.5 % experienced changes in their attitude and even lesser portion experienced changes in their behaviour.

13 Around 74 % students recommended using the online streaming services. 19.7% might recommend it and 1.5% would recommend a particular show or series. 5.3% would not recommend using these services.

Recommendation for a video streaming service or a show

(Source: Authors' own contribution)

14. If given an option of spending time on something other than online streaming, 35.7 % would spend time on social media and 27% would socialise. Activities like watching television and listening to podcasts were voted by 11.1% and 7.9 % of students. Activities like reading, gym, playing sports like football, sketching were preferred by 0.8% students or less each. 7.9 % claimed they would not spend time on other of these activities.

streaming services, they would prefer social media next and then to socialise.

VII. CONCLUSION

It is evident from the analysed data that a very significant majority consumes online video streaming services. The top three platforms are YouTube, Netflix and Hotstar. Online streaming services are one of the major sources of entertainment they are increasingly becoming part of daily lives of student. A good number of students use these services every day.

One of the most important reasons why college going young adults choose online video streaming services is freedom of choice. The next reason was mobility and what is trending. They want to watch their choice of show at their own time, unlike television shows which are aired on particular days and time. The top 3 genres were Thriller, Comedy and fiction.

A good number of college going young adults admit that their schedule is affected because of these services. Huge number of these consumers prefer one service provider over the other because of availability of exclusive content.

A good number of these consumers believe that watching these shows have changed their way of thinking or perception towards reality. A significant number of these consumers recommend using online video streaming services. If they are not spending time on video

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